

Refining Audience Engagement: Leveraging Text-based Audience Comments as an Evolution Metric in Small 501(c)(3) Advocacy-Focused Nonprofits

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Abstract: This study examines how small, Los Angeles-based, advocacy-focused nonprofit organizations (NPOs) use Facebook to engage audiences through information sharing, calls for action, and community-building. More importantly, it explores text-based audience comments—a novel metric for measuring audience engagement in social media studies in advocacy-focused nonprofit organizations (advocacy-NPOs). Rather than relying solely on traditional metrics (e.g., frequency of “likes,” “comments,” and “shares” of NPO-generated posts), we analyzed user-generated content such as text-based audience comments to capture nuanced engagement as well as audience preferences and interactions. The findings reveal that NPO-generated posts prioritized *Information* (92%) and *Action* (71.3%) categories, with limited focus on the *Community*. By contrast, text-based audience comments were most common in the *Community* category (80.3%), with frequent replies to NPOs including expressions of gratitude and demonstrations of support. This discrepancy between NPOs’ organizational posts emphasis on Information and audiences’ preference for community underscores the importance of peer interaction and social bonding as primary motivators for engagement. Additionally, both NPO-generated posts and text-based audience comments contained advocacy-focused content, so this pattern reflects alignment between organizational missions and audience interests. These insights can help advocacy-NPOs develop practical strategies to enhance their social media impact and strengthen audience engagement.

Keywords: Social Media Engagement, Advocacy Nonprofits, Facebook, Audience Comments

Introduction

Social media has revolutionized how nonprofit organizations (NPOs) engage with their audiences. It not only provides an efficient channel for exchanging information and mobilizing collective action but also helps boost NPOs’ reputation (Namisango et al., 2019). Aligned with NPOs’ core mission to address social objectives, these interactive functions have driven the widespread adoption of social media among NPOs. Social media, especially for smaller NPOs, is a cost-effective communication tool for expanding outreach and maintaining meaningful engagement with supporters (Campbell et al., 2013; Guo & Saxton, 2014; Zhang et al., 2013).

According to the 2023 Nonprofit Tech for Good Report, approximately 91% of NPOs in the United States maintain official websites, which illustrates their widespread digital presence. Among social media platforms, Facebook is the most popular and is used by 96% of surveyed NPOs, followed by Instagram (73%), Twitter (59%), LinkedIn (49%), and YouTube (44%; 2023 Nonprofit Tech for Good Report, 2023).

Research indicates that 55% of people who engage with NPOs on social media subsequently take action to support those NPOs' missions (NP Source, 2022). Social media has reshaped the nature of interactions between NPOs and their audiences by helping to deepen existing relationships, and simultaneously reach new audiences (Schmitz et al., 2020). Online fundraising has also emerged as a crucial revenue source, particularly for smaller NPOs, which raised 18% of their total funds from digital channels—this applies even more to larger organizations (Blackbaud Institute, 2022).

Beyond Audience Comments

While most social media studies in the nonprofit sector have focused on quantifying engagement to measure audience interactions by counting the number of “likes”, “comments”, and “shares” of posts, scholars have increasingly recognized that these metrics only touch the surface of audience interaction (Appleby, 2016). Although qualitative analysis offers a deeper understanding of NPO-generated posts, most research to date has only focused on analyzing messages from X (formerly Twitter; Anagnostopoulos et al., 2017). We believe user-generated content, such as text-based audience comments, could provide deeper insights into how individuals (collectively, the audience) perceive, respond to, and participate in advocacy efforts with NPOs online. Therefore, further exploration of the qualitative dimension, particularly audience interactions, beyond traditional metrics, is essential for a comprehensive understanding of social media effectiveness of advocacy-NPOs (i.e., nonprofit organizations that have advocacy as their core mission). By analyzing these comments, advocacy-NPOs can gain a nuanced understanding of what content captures their audience's attention, how messages resonate with their audience, and how they motivate community members to act. This understanding is especially critical for advocacy-NPOs, where community building plays a vital role in achieving organizational goals.

Advocacy organizations are entities dedicated to shaping public policy and community opinion on chosen issues, interests, or causes (Hojnacki et al., 2012; Schlozman et al., 2015). These groups use a range of tactics, including lobbying, public campaigns, and litigation, to achieve their social, political, environmental, and economic goals. In this study, we focused on advocacy-NPOs that are registered as 501(c)(3) organizations, as defined by the Internal Revenue Service (IRS), and excluded 501(c)(4) and 501(h) organizations. Social media has transformed how these advocacy-NPOs communicate. With social media platforms, these advocacy-NPOs can interact with both their members and the public in real time (Bürger, 2015; Guo & Saxton, 2014; Saxton & Wang, 2014). The decentralized nature of social media platforms facilitates two-way communication, promotes deeper audience interaction, and amplifies the impact of advocacy initiatives (Seelig et al., 2019). Additionally, they can enhance public discourse, mobilize supporters, and transform traditional strategies for public engagement.

Literature Review

Although the value of social media in NPOs is widely acknowledged, few studies have explored how text-based audience comments shape social media engagement in the context of NPO advocacy (Appleby, 2016). This study helps fill this gap by systematically analyzing both NPO-generated posts and the associated text-based audience comments to better understand how information, action, and communities interact in digital spaces.

Evolution of Engagement Metrics

The evolution of measurement engagement within NPOs has shifted from relying on quantitative metrics (e.g., frequencies of “likes,” “comments,” and “shares”) toward

adopting more nuanced and interpretive frameworks. Sentiment analysis, one example of quantitative analysis, has emerged as a data-driven approach that categorizes messages as positive, neutral, or negative feedback and adds interpretive dimensions to engagement assessment (Balfour, 2020; Bhati & McDonnell, 2024).

Although traditional metrics remain dominant, these approaches have been criticized for their inability to capture the depth of stakeholder interactions and audience preferences. Lovejoy and Saxton's (2012) pioneered qualitative content analysis to examine nonprofits communication strategies. Building on this, Campbell and Lambright (2020) argued that effective engagement analysis should transcend mere numerical counts and include qualitative analysis of posts that reflect community and stakeholder relationships. Ksiazek et al. (2016) highlighted the value of analyzing user-generated comments as qualitative analysis of audience comments can generate deeper insights into user preferences and organizational engagement practices.

The Emergence of Community-Building as a Strategic Focus for Advocacy-NPOs

Despite the growing recognition of community building as critical for online engagement, limited research has explored how advocacy-NPOs use social media to build communities with their supporters. Lovejoy and Saxton (2012) introduced the "information-community-action" framework for NPOs' social media strategies. They emphasized that community-building messages are crucial for deepening engagement, especially in an advocacy context. Guo and Saxton (2014) subsequently found that advocacy-NPOs used social media not only to share information or solicitations for action but also to build communities of supporters around shared causes.

Further studies suggest that community-related content typically generates higher audience engagement than information-only posts (Maxwell & Carboni, 2016; Xue et al., 2024), because audiences tend to show stronger preferences for content that fosters a sense of community over purely informational messaging (Campbell et al., 2013; Ksiazek et al., 2016). Morgan et al. (2024) examined how NPOs leverage the social media platform TikTok to enhance their missions, as the fast-changing nature of TikTok challenges NPOs' traditional long-term planning models.

Text-based Audience Comments as an Authentic Measure of Engagement

Text-based audience comments offer richer and more authentic insights into engagement than quantifiable metrics represented as numerical totals associated with a post, and even NPO-generated posts. Traditional metrics are critiqued for providing a surface-level assessment of engagement by overlooking the qualitative dimensions inherent in user interaction (Baccarella et al., 2021). Furthermore, NPO-generated posts tend to be creator-centered rather than audience focused, so they could not directly reflect the genuine audience preferences. Xue et al. (2024) emphasized the significance of user-generated content (e.g., text-based audience comments) in promoting authentic connections between NPOs and their audiences; their exploration supported analyzing text-based audience comments as a means of engagement. Empirical inquiries demonstrate this distinction as Young et al. (2020) suggested that the comments could serve as indicators of deeper engagement on health promotion interventions. Liadeli et al. (2022) observed that users' comments may indicate a higher level of user involvement compared to quantitative metrics and provide richer insights into preferences and the development of community. DeMasters et al. (2024) stated that NPOs' TikTok content, which is community-oriented, does not align with their information-sharing strategies. This discrepancy suggests that audience-generated comments rather than NPO-generated content more accurately represent authentic community engagement.

Research Questions

According to social presence theory, the more interactive and social a platform is, the greater its engagement levels tend to be, as users are encouraged to express themselves, share experiences, build relationships, and receive feedback (Men et al., 2018). Therefore, these concepts were applied to measure engagement levels and identify relevant content by focusing on higher levels of engagement. Based on those theoretical foundations, we develop the following questions:

RQ1: How do small, Los Angeles-based NPOs engage their audiences on Facebook to share information, call for action, and build communities?

RQ2: To what functions or purposes (information sharing, action mobilization, or community building) do text-based audience comments respond in Facebook posts by small, Los Angeles-based NPOs?

Methodology

Data Collection and Reasoning

The dataset was created by selecting NPOs from the most current version (April 2022) of Nonprofit Explorer. The selection criteria for the NPO population and final samples are detailed in Appendix Table A1. A total of 505, a verified dataset size, organizational posts from seven NPOs were collected over a three-month period (July 1 to September 30, 2022) using web scraping tools. Of the 505 posts, 150 were randomly sampled for data analysis, and 76 of the 149 audience comments corresponded to the 150 NPO-generated posts employing standard data science techniques such as descriptive statistics (e.g., measures of central tendency).

The sample sizes of 150 posts and 76 corresponding text-based audience comments were selected for two main reasons. First, the basic unit of analysis was the content of a Facebook message, not an individual NPO. Prior research on NPO communication and public marketing has demonstrated that social media messages, especially Facebook posts, which do not have character limits, are information-rich and suitable for both qualitative and quantitative analyses (Dolan et al., 2019). When content analysis is employed, the basic unit is a message (e.g., a Facebook post) rather than an organization. Because each message can be represented as a data point, a sufficiently large sample of messages that are rich in content and engagement cues is likely to generate meaningful insights (Dolan et al., 2019). Second, two preliminary pilot studies were conducted to refine the criteria for assessing social media content between NPOs and their audiences (Appendix Table A2). The pilot findings confirmed that small-scale analyses of social media posts can generate critical insights by identifying practical details such as appropriate research methods, optimal periods for data collection, and the most suitable social media platform (Julious, 2005).

Data Analysis and Coding Procedure

Our analysis followed a mixed-methods approach, a descriptive quantitative analysis of engagement metrics as well as a qualitative thematic analysis of the 150 NPO-generated posts utilizing web scraping tools, and the 76 text-based audience comments. Then, the results were compared and examined by using data science classification models to avoid human bias. Specifically, we conducted a descriptive quantitative analysis of engagement metrics to provide summary insights including central tendency and spread, comparative summaries and percentages. We then performed a qualitative analysis to categorize the messages into three labels (i.e., information, community, and action), using MAXODA, a content coding framework. The coded messages were further examined and compared using large language model (LLM) systems from the machine learning field.

For the deductive analysis, all NPO-generated posts and audience comments were categorized into three areas (information, community, and action) and coded based on the 11 subcategories from Lovejoy and Saxton (2012) along with two additional subcategories (mission and organizational information) from Campbell and Lambright (2018). An inductive analysis was used to identify new subcategories within each category (information, action, and community). Each Facebook message, all NPO-generated posts and audience comments, was coded by segment, allowing for multiple codes per message, thereby capturing the complexity of audience engagement with the content (Denq, 2024).

Results

Qualitative analysis of NPO-generated posts

We classified NPO-generated posts on Facebook into three categories (*Information, Action, or Community*) and further broke down accompanying subcategories to catch more nuanced meaning.

Information category posts (with added advocacy-related subcategory)

During the coding process, one subcategory—advocacy—was identified inductively for information-related messaging (Table 1). Advocacy-NPOs primarily focused on reinforcing their organizational mission, vision, and values, with raising awareness of their advocacy initiatives and brand identity as the top priority. With 39 posts, event-related content constituted a significant proportion, including detailed (particularly advocacy-oriented) events of NPO communication that often combined calls for volunteers or other actions (Denq, 2024). Advocacy-related *Information* focused on relevant legislation or regulations, providing a link to contact legislators or local policymakers, which ranked among the top three content categories. This subcategory identified through inductive analysis is proposed as an addition to the *Information* category within our framework, especially for advocacy-NPOs.

Table 1. Subcategories of *Information* Category Posts

Subcategory	Key contents	#Post	As a % of all information-related posts (138 posts/ 175 codes)
Mission	Information related to its specific mission to raise awareness of the organization's brand	88	63.77%/50.29%
Events	Information to promote organizational events/activities	39	22.29%/28.26%
Advocacy (New)	Information-related advocacy and lobbying such as policies or petitions	25	6.8%/18.12%
Organizational	Information related to organizational programs, services, board members, or photos posts for events	23	6.3%/16.67%
Total	Single, double, or triple codes	175	

Action category posts

For the 107 action-related messages, the analysis presented is in Table 2. The most common goal was the promotion of an event and inviting the audience to join. Action-related posts were divided into several subcategories, based on specific NPO goals. The primary goal was to promote an event and invite an audience to join. This content category was followed by action posts designed to empower audience members in specific ways by “learning how to help.” The requests to “learn how to help” entailed specific actions in support of the mission, especially for organizations with more complicated social issues such as homelessness. The third most important category was lobbying and advocacy, which often included requests to contact public officials or local representatives regarding relevant policies.

Table 2. Subcategories of *Action* Category Posts

Subcategory	Key contents	# Posts	As a percentage 107 posts/150 codes
Promoting an event	Invite audience to attend the event or activities	41	27.32%/27.33%
Learn how to help	Request to learn how to help NPOs	38	25.33%/25.33%
Lobbying and advocacy	Request that the audience contact public officials to lobby for policies or petitions	21	14.00%/14.00%
Following the organization on social media	Invite the audience to follow NPOs on official websites or social media sites	15	10.02%/10.00%
Donation appeal	Request monetary and in-kind donations	14	13.08%/9.33%
Know the NPOs better (new)	Request to read/learn more information about organizations such as missions	10	10.35%/6.67%
All others (miscellaneous)	Recruit volunteers and employees; join another site or vote for the organization; posted positive feedback	11	10.33%/7.28%
Total	Double or triple codes	150	

Community category posts

The community-related messages served to interact, share, and communicate with audiences (or stakeholders) to eventually facilitate online and offline community-building. Table 3 provides a breakdown of these messages based on three major subcategories. The first subcategory was “mentions and acknowledgments” of current and local events that were not initiated by the organization itself as well as giving thanks and recognition. The second subcategory, “giving recognition and thanks,” represents acknowledging the contributions of supporters, volunteers, and followers. This type of message received the largest number of comments, with most thank you messages related to direct services, rather than financial support. Community-related messages reflect NPOs’ broad

perspectives on social issues as they engage larger audiences through their organizational or personal affiliations.

Table 3. Subcategories of *Community* Category Posts

Subcategory	Key contents	# of Posts	As a percentage of (37 posts/47 codes)
Acknowledgment of current and local events (by affiliated organizations)	Events not initiated by the organization	25	67.57%/53.19%
Giving recognition and thanks	Recognition of individuals or groups	19	51.35%/41.43%
Responses to replied to messages	Responses as interactive communication	3	8.11%/6.38%
Total	Double and triple codes	47	

Qualitative Analysis of Text-based Audience Comments and Their Engagement Levels

The audience comments were analyzed and separated into three categories—*Information*, *Community*, and *Action*—based on the framework from Lovejoy and Saxton (2012). In Tables 4, 5, and 6, text-based audience comments displayed a dominant interest in *Community*-related content, followed by *Action* and *Information* categories.

Information category text-based audience comments

In Table 4, *Information*-related comments (a total of thirty-eight comments) from the audience were also classified under each of the four sub-categories: mission, events, advocacy, and organization-related. Among audience comments, information-related interactions primarily focused on mission-related discussions and highlighted significant engagement with narratives about homelessness and organizational missions. Despite being the least frequent category, mission-focused content elicits substantial audience interaction.

Table 4. Text-based Audience Comments Across *Information* Subcategories

	Key contents	# of subcategories coded	As a % of total information contents messages (37 comments/37 codes)
Mission	Comments on organizational mission	24	63.89%
Event	Comments about advocacy	6	16.67%
Advocacy	Comments on events	4	11.11%
Organization	Comments on organization	3	8.33%
Total	Single, double, and triple codes	37	

Action-related text-based audience comments

As Table 5 shows, *Action*-related comments accounted for a notable portion of audience responses and emphasized support for NPO activities and community advocacy. This category exhibited dynamic engagement in which audiences expressed support, provided positive feedback, and participated in advocacy efforts.

Table 5. Text-based Audience Comments Across Action Subcategories

	Key contents	# of subcategories coded	As a % of total information contents messages (44 comments/63 codes)
Help NPOs and their audience	Comments about the actions the audience did voluntarily to support organizations and their community	21	33.33%/47.73%
Other-replied with positive feedback	Comments to provide positive feedback to organization and other users' posts	14	22.22%/31.82%
Advocacy and lobbying	Comments to advocate for NPOs and request to vote or contact local representative for NPOs	9	14.29%/20.45%
Questions about how to help	Comments to inquire about how to support NPOs and audience help	9	14.29%/20.45%
Knowing the organization better	Comments to express their intention to better know the organization by acting as the audience suggested	8	12.70%/18.18%
Donation appeal	Comments in response to donation request	2	3.17%/4.55%
Total		63	

Community-related text-based audience comments

Based on Table 5, the most engaged category—*Community*-related comments—demonstrated a vibrant interaction among the audience, with discussions centering on public replies, expressions of gratitude, and shared support for organizational endeavors.

Table 6. Content Comments Across Community Subcategories

	Key contents	# of subcategories coded	As a % of total information content messages 62 comments/97 codes
Public replies	The audience replied to other audiences' posts (or NPOs' posts)	30	48.39%/30.9%
Giving recognition and thanks	The audience expressed appreciation for the organizational works	26	41.94%/26.8%
Demonstrate the support	The audience validated the relationship with the NPOs	23	37.10%/23.71%
Sharing current news and local events	The audience shared current and local events related to NPOs (not initiated by NPOs)	18	29.03%/18.56%
Total		97	

The Comparison of NPO-generated Posts and Accompanying Text-based Audience Comments by Content Category

Table 7 provides the classification of the 150 NPO-generated samples and accompanying 76 text-based audience comments according to the content focused on information, action, or community. The findings revealed that Information distribution was the primary purpose in 92% of NPO-generated posts, compared with 48% of text-based audience comments had this focus. Calls for action appeared in 71.3% of NPO posts but in only 57.9% of text-based audience comments. Community-building was discovered in 24.7% of NPO posts, while a substantial 80.3% of text-based audience comments focused on this category.

Table 7. Comparing Organizational and User-generated Foci

	Community	Action	Information
Organizational posts (n=150)	24.7% (37)	71.3% (107)	92% (138)
Audience comments (n=76)	80.3% (62)	57.9% (44)	48% (37)

Discussion & Conclusion

Similarity in Prevalence of Advocacy between NPO-generated Posts and Text-based Audience Comments

The advocacy-related content categorized under *Information* and *Action* may have gained popularity for two reasons: the high alignment between NPOs' missions and their audience's interests, and the expanded criteria helped to identify advocacy-related content (Tables 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5). We found that the higher the alignment between NPOs' mission

and their audience's interests, the higher the audience engagement—as shown in previous work (Huang et al., 2016). This alignment underscores how the commitment of these advocacy-NPOs to their advocacy goals can actively engage audiences who value the same mission. The high level of engagement demonstrates a direct impact on the NPOs' advocacy efforts such as supporting activities, providing positive feedback, and participating in lobbying processes. This suggests that these NPOs can effectively mobilize their communities to enhance their impact. Thus, more advocacy-related content could be found.

The second reason could stem from expanding the criteria to identify advocacy-related content. Traditionally, researchers relied on comparative narrow indicators such as policy petition or lobbying, grouped under the “lobbying” subcategory (Tables 1 and 2). However, our findings proved that a broader approach uncovers additional advocacy-related content, including community-related messages under “*Information*” and “*Action*” categories. Lovejoy and Saxton et al (2012) noted that community-related messages could classified under “recognition or thanks” subcategories well represent advocacy (Lovejoy and Saxton et al 2012). The main themes they identified align closely with our findings such as contents “expressions of commitment” and “encouragement” from the audience. Building on this insight, we developed a dedicated “Advocacy” subcategory that captures the sense of community expressed through sharing information or calling action within “*Information*” and “*Action*” categories, so we provide a more comprehensive representation of advocacy-related content.

Discrepancy in Engagement Preferences Between NPO-generated Posts and Text-based Audience Comments

The most significant finding appears in messages in the “*Community*” category. While only a small portion of NPO-generated posts were community-related (24.7%), most audience comments were community-related (80.3%), including public replies (48.39%), expressions of appreciation (41.94%), and demonstrating support for NPO initiatives (37.10%; Table 1). This discrepancy supports the importance of social bonding and peer interaction as primary motivators for engagement. Additionally, it indicates that audiences are more inclined to participate in discussions that validate their relationships with NPOs than to respond to announcements or action solicitations. Interestingly, this challenges the traditional belief of using comments under “action” as an indicator of engagement instead of “community.”

This finding could provide effective implications about how NPOs could structure their communication strategies to maximize audience interaction. This may be particularly helpful in the context of advocacy outreach, in which aligning content with audience preferences is desired for effectiveness (Tarifa-Rodríguez, 2023; Zhang, 2022).

Based on the similarity and discrepancy mentioned above, text-based audience comments not only contained high advocacy-related content but also reflected genuine audience interests. To date, there seems to be no established formulas that can well explain the relationship between text-based audience comments and audience preferences, which are highly desired by NPOs.

Optional Measure for Engagement—Text-based Audience Comments with Qualitative Analysis

To our knowledge, this research is the first study that uses “text-based audience comments,” which can well reflect audience preference, to measure audience engagement. Studies conducted on platforms such as TikTok (DeMasters et al., 2024) also supported our findings that NPOs use community-focused content to facilitate other functions, such as information sharing and action-taking. These conclusions align with our qualitative analysis

of text-based audience comments. Specifically, if researchers hope to increase audience engagement, using community-focused content will be more effective than using information-oriented content, despite previous research identifying that as most of the content posted by NPOs.

Studying audience engagement by using text-based audience comments has many advantages. First, while most researchers focus on qualitative analysis by interviewing participants, our approach could avoid inherent biases in the interview methods, in which participant responses may be influenced by the presence of an observer (Bernard et al., 1984). Furthermore, existing literature supports the idea that customer-generated content, such as text-based audience comments, has a greater impact on their trust level toward the NPOs than NPO-generated messages. This is important because the trust has been shown to highly correlate with audience's intention of engagement, which implies "intent to purchase" in for-profit contexts (Nikbin et al., 2022).

Limitation and Future Studies

This study has some limitations. First, the research sample included only a small number of Los Angeles-based NPOs from ProPublica's Nonprofit Explorer database. Even though some findings may be applicable to 501(c)(3) NPOs with similar NTEE codes, they cannot be generalized to all small NPOs in Los Angeles or the whole United States. Second, Facebook was the only social media platform analyzed in this study. This report did not examine NPO messages on other platforms, such as Instagram, which relies more heavily on visual content than Facebook.

Future studies could study how different message types or other factors could impact audience engagement. For instance, because this study included a limited number of participants from each category (three health, one education, one human resource, one environmental, and one political/societal benefit-community), the impact of the type of NPOs (NTEE codes) remains unknown.

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DENQ & HSU: Refining Audience Engagement: Leveraging Text-based Audience Comments as an Evolution Metric in Small 501(c)(3) Advocacy-Focused Nonprofits

Appendix A

Table A1. Inclusion Criteria for Advocacy-NPOs

Elements	Criteria	Rationale
NPOs type	501(c)(3) (excluding IRS 501(c)(4) and 501(h))	To distinguish from political organizations that focus on political activities overlapping with advocacy
Size	<\$500,000 for at least 3 years 2018–2020	For covering smaller NPOs (bias: 100-style sampling)
Geography	Los Angeles Metro Area (Including 5 counties: Los Angeles County, Orange County, Riverside County, San Bernardino County, Ventura County)	For increasing the understanding of LA-based NPOs due to resident familiarity (bias: limited studies)
Activities	Must include “advocacy” in a mission statement or description of significant activities (e.g., web presence, annual reports, 990 forms)	For exploring the depth of the activities of NPOs for advocacy
Sectoral background	Sectors for relevance in LA: environment, health, education, human service-food, public community, housing shelter, and uncategorized	For multiple categories (bias: only advocate organizations as a single category)
Communication level	Facebook as a major communication tool	To catch major and recent posts on social media platforms

Note: Out of 5,683 nonprofits in the Greater Los Angeles metro area initially considered for study, only 14 organizations met all inclusion criteria and were included in the final sample list. From this list, 10 NPOs were purposefully selected for different NTEE codes. Finally, three NPOs were excluded from the final sample list because of their poor representation of the population (i.e., NPOs’ posts on Facebook accounts), with only two, four, and eight posts over three months. Consequently, a total of seven NPOs were examined.

Table A2. The major findings of two pilot studies

	Study 1	Study 2
Study period	16 days (March 16–31, 2022)	15 days (April 1–15, 2022)
Questions	How do large NPOs use Twitter to engage audiences for advocacy?	How do small Los Angeles-based NPOs use Twitter to engage their audiences for advocacy?
Study subject	2 large NPOs	10 small NPOs
Study subject activities	Food Bank and Environment	Environment, Education, Human Services (youth development...), Unclassified, Public Benefit, etc.
Posts investigated	More than 250 posts, but lost tracking manually	132 posts with 302 codes (code analysis)
Supporter comments investigated	More than 150 content comments, but lost tracking	125 content comments
Findings	<p>It was difficult to manually code a large number of posts. Software supporting coding is preferable.</p> <p>The content of Twitter is limited, and most posts are due to Twitter’s 140/280-character limit in single postings.</p>	<p>It was found that Twitter was not a major communication tool for the majority of the sampled NPOs.</p> <p>The source dataset (Great Nonprofits) website did not have the majority of Los Angeles NPOs. This prompted switching to Nonprofit Explorer.</p> <p>It was not possible to use the Ncapture function in NVivo.</p> <p>The preliminary results of the descriptive analysis suggested using tools such as Excel ,SPSS or data science tools (i.e., Python library) for quantitative analysis and helped define the study timeframe (3 months).</p>